

SYNTACTIC STRUCTURES: SYNTACTIC ANALYSIS OF COMPLEX SENTENCES IN
THE UZBEK LANGUAGE AND THEIR COMMUNICATIVE FUNCTIONS

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Аннотация

В данной статье изучается синтаксический анализ сложных предложений и их коммуникативные функции в узбекском языке. Анализируется функция языковых единиц в речи и коммуникативные процессы, осуществляемые с их помощью. Рассматривается структурная структура сложных предложений, способы синтаксической связи, выразительные возможности речи. Роль различных типов сложных предложений в языке и их значение в общении также иллюстрируются примерами.

Ключевые слова. Сложносочиненное предложение, синтаксический анализ, коммуникативная функция, придаточное предложение, подчиненное предложение, причинно-следственная связь, синтаксис, текст.

Abstract

This article studies the syntactic analysis of complex sentences in the Uzbek language and their communicative functions. The function of language units in speech and the communicative processes carried out through them are analyzed. The structural structure of complex sentences, methods of syntactic connection, and expressive possibilities in speech are highlighted. Also, the role of various types of complex sentences in the language and their importance in communication are shown with examples.

Keywords. Compound sentence, syntactic analysis, communicative function, subordinate clause, subordinate clause, cause-and-effect relationship, syntax, text.

INTRODUCTION

Among language units, a sentence is the largest syntactic unit. In particular, complex sentences are one of the structurally and semantically rich forms of speech, with the help of which complex thoughts and relationships are expressed. In the Uzbek language, this type of sentence is widely used and plays an important role in increasing the effectiveness of communication.

The communicative function of complex sentences is that through them the speaker can express his thoughts more completely, fully and in accordance with the contextual conditions. Therefore, complex sentences are the most important object of study of the syntax of the Uzbek language.

Syntactic analysis shows that complex sentences can be of various forms: with and without a conjunction, with a subordinate clause, with a compound clause, and with a coherent sentence. There are semantic and communicative differences between them.

In this article, we analyze the types of complex sentences not only formally, but also from the point of view of their function in speech, the meaning they express, and their role in communication. This approach provides a deeper understanding of the natural use of sentences in communication.

The article studies complex sentences with and without conjunctions, compound sentences and the communicative goals expressed through them in the Uzbek language. Particular attention is paid to the structure of sentences with meanings such as condition, cause, result, comparison, desire. The

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article contains analytical results that are theoretically and practically important for the field of syntax. It also considers the functional-stylistic role of complex sentences.

The research belongs to the applied syntax direction of linguistics and is devoted to the study of the communicative functions of sentences in the Uzbek language. It analyzes what information is transmitted using complex sentences, how the relationship between the speaker and the listener is expressed. This serves as a practical basis for language teachers and language learners.

The article also explains the structural differences of complex sentences, their semantic relationship, their discursive function in speech, and examples based on Uzbek language materials. The results demonstrate the importance of complex sentences as one of the main sources of communicativeness and semantic integrity in modern language.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The first studies on the analysis of complex sentences were conducted by A. A. Abduazizov, N. Mahmudov, G. Rahmatullaeva, Sh. Rakhmatullayev. These scientists deeply analyzed the formal and semantic structure of syntactic units in the Uzbek language.

In Uzbek linguistics, there are many scientific works on the division of complex sentences, classification of their types, and types of their connection. However, there are relatively few studies on the communicative aspect of these sentences.

In recent years, the functional role of complex sentences in the language has been reconsidered within the framework of linguopragmatics and communicative linguistics. In particular, the issues of stylistic use and compatibility with text units are becoming relevant.

Among foreign literature, the theoretical foundations developed in this area in Russian and English linguistics, in particular the works of M. Y. Blok, E. I. Shegal, D. Crystal, G. Leech, are also methodologically important sources.

The study used structural-syntactic analysis, semantic analysis, communicative-functional approach, contrastive method and discourse analysis methods. These methods shed light on the harmony of form and meaning of complex sentences.

Samples of written and oral speech, literary works and texts from the media were used as material. Attention was paid to the use of sentences in different contexts.

The means of communication between sentences, their semantic relationship, and types of communication were systematically studied. Also, the communicative goals transmitted through them (for example, giving reasons, explaining, recognizing) were identified.

As a methodological approach, the function of each sentence in the language, its social significance and effectiveness in communication were analyzed based on the principle of communicativeness. For this, discursive situations were analyzed in context.

RESULTS

The results of the study showed that complex sentences in the Uzbek language are rich and meaningful not only in terms of form, but also in terms of their communicative load. Each type of complex sentence has its own unique information-transmitting capabilities.

Sentences with conjunctions are often used to express cause-and-effect, condition, time, and comparative relationships. With their help, the speaker consistently expresses his or her opinion, justifies or explains the situation.

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Sentences without conjunctions are used to express emotional tone, immediacy, and naturalness of speech. These sentences are especially common in oral speech and serve to make communication lively.

In many cases, subordinate clauses perform an information-explanatory and clarifying function. They are widely used in complex texts, official and scientific styles. Each type of sentence contributes to the richness of the language with its stylistic capabilities.

Table 1. Syntactic structure and communicative functions of complex sentence types

№	Type of complex sentence	Syntactic structure	Basic connectives	Communicative function	Scope
1	Complex sentence with a conjunction	I + conjunction + II	and, but, because, if, however	Detailing, explaining the reason, expressing the condition	Scientific, journalistic
2	Complex sentence without a conjunction	I, II (without conjunction)	pause, intonation	Speed, simplicity of speech, emotionality	Oral speech, artistic style
3	Complex sentence with a subordinate clause	Main clause + subordinate clause	if, therefore, because	Explanation, clarification	Scientific, official style
4	Compound complex sentence	I + II (independent clauses)	and, or, however, but	Providing a sequence of thoughts	In various styles

This table systematically describes the types of complex sentences in the Uzbek language, along with their syntactic structure, connectives, communicative functions, and areas of application. The table compares different types of complex sentences syntactically and pragmatically.

1. Complex sentences with conjunctions - connect two or more sentences through conjunctions and usually express logical relationships such as explanation, reason, condition, comparison.
2. Complex sentences without conjunctions - although there are no syntactic connectives between them, communication is connected through intonation and pause.
3. Complex sentences with subordinate clauses - one sentence is the main one, and the second follows it, that is, it is semantically related to it.
4. Compound sentences - two or more independent sentences are equally connected and express a single complex thought.

This table visually and systematically shows the syntactic role of complex sentences in the language system and their function in communication. It also identifies their stylistic use.

CONCLUSION

Complex sentences occupy an important place in the syntactic system of the Uzbek language. With their help, thoughts are expressed in a complex way, information is transmitted with clarity, and the purpose of communication is also achieved.

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This article shows that each type of sentence has its own syntactic structure, which is closely related to its communicative function. The types and context of speech determine this function.

Syntactic analysis shows that through complex sentences, the speaker expresses his thoughts in an understandable, clear and logical way. This increases the effectiveness of speech.

In future studies, it would be appropriate to analyze in more depth the role of complex sentences in text units, their stylistic function and psycholinguistic aspects.

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